

HAITI

GIS-BASED HYDROPOWER POTENTIAL MAPPING ATLAS

March 2021

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1 INTRODUCTION

Haiti is a mountainous country that shares the western third of the island of Hispaniola with the Dominican Republic. The island has favorable topographic, and hydrological conditions that lead to the creation of many streams and rivers. Haiti alone has more than 170 rivers and streams that could be used as a source of energy. In the past, many of these rivers were utilized to power local water wheels for the processing of sugar cane. During the 1970s and 1980s a few modern hydropower plants were constructed for the production of electricity. However, development of new hydropower facilities has been hampered by the lack of reliable estimate of the available potential.

This study has evaluated multiple potential sites by using relevant available data. These data were useful in spotting potential sites, in estimating flow regime at ungauged streams, and in evaluating the potential power and energy at these sites. The main approach for this study was to utilize the capability of Geographical Information System (GIS) to locate many potential sites while limiting field visits. Calibration and validation of streamflow data were performed from available historical river gauge flow data.

A GIS based analysis of potential hydropower sites is useful for planning and prioritizing development projects for government entities, developers, and renewable energy companies. This is a fast procedure to quantify available potential. The preliminary identification and ranking of these sites will provide the justification for further in-depth studies.

2 EXISTING HYDROPOWER FACILITIES

In Haiti there are a number of public and private hydroelectric facilities that have been constructed and operated either as stand-alone or connected to the national grid. Many of these facilities have been in operations for years.

2.1 PUBLICLY OWNED FACILITIES

There are seven publicly owned hydroelectric facilities totalizing 60,800 KW currently installed in Haiti. These facilities are summarized in Table 2-1 below, and in Exhibit A-4 of Appendix A.

SITE NAME	TURBINE TYPE	TURBINE AMOUNT	INSTALLED CAPACITY (KW)	ANNUAL ENERGY (KWH)
Caracol	Pelton	1	800	4,000,000
Drouet	Cross-flow	4	2,500	6,000,000
Deluge/Lanzac	Pelton	2	1,100	4,700,000
Saut-Mathurine	Francis	2	1,600	3,000,000
Gaillard	Pelton	1	500	3,800,000
Onde Verte	Cross-flow	2	300	1,900,000
Peligre	Francis	3	54,000	215,800,000

Table 2-1 Publicly Owned Hydroelectric Facilities.

2.2 PRIVATELY OWNED FACILITIES

There are four privately owned hydroelectric facilities. There are being used to provide energy to local hospitals, and local cooperatives. These private facilities are summarized in Table 2-2 below.

SITE NAME	DEPARTMENT	TURBINE TYPE	TURBINE AMOUNT	INSTALLED CAPACITY (KW)
Hospital Belfin	Sud	Pelton	1	NA
Café Lompré	Ouest	Pelton	1	NA
Magazen	Nord Est	Pelton	1	11
Cange	Centre	Francis	3	NA

Table 2-2 Privately Owned Hydroelectric Facilities

3 PREVIOUS ESTIMATES ON HYDROPOWER POTENTIAL

Over the years various studies and estimates of the potential were performed. The earliest study was performed by the Canadian International Development Agency (CIDA). Subsequent studies and spotting of potential sites were performed by the Ministry of Public Works, Transport, and Communications (TPTC). As new sites are being spotted, there are added on an inventory list maintained by TPTC. A newer estimate of the potential was performed in 2011 by SOLEO Energies and published by the Worldwatch Institute in 2014.

3.1 ESTIMATES PER CIDA

In 1976, the Canadian firm of Lalonde, Girouard, Letendre, and Associates (LGL) under contract from CIDA performed an extensive survey of all the potential hydroelectric sites within the country. The site spotting criteria they used was to investigate all rivers with a drop of 20 meters on the contour maps. Once spotted the investigating firm used a helicopter to investigate further these sites. On site flow measurements were also performed. A total of twelve sites were inventoried. These sites are summarized in Table 3-1 below (Lalonde, Girouard, Letendre & Associates, 1976).

SITE NAME	DEPARTMENT	POTENTIAL CAPACITY (KW)
Saut du Barril	Nippes	364
Bassin Bleu	Nord Est	129
La Gosseline	Sud Est	153
Pichon	Sud Est	1,234
Momance	Ouest	1,120
Deluge	Artibonite	1,180
Gobe	Artibonite	190
Saut d’Eau	Ouest	670
Roche Plate	Centre	2,570
Samana	Centre	776
Caracol	Nord	282
Petite Riviere	Nord	130

Table 3-1 Estimate of Haiti’s hydropower potential per CIDA (1976)

Per this list the sites of Deluge, and Caracol were constructed. Other detailed studies of additional sites were performed by LGL for the following rivers:

- River Artibonite
- River Grande Anse
- River of Trois Rivieres
- River Guayamouc
- River La Theme
- River Grise

These detailed studies were not available for consultation during the writing of this document, but fortunately the sites general estimated capacity is noted in the database maintained by TPTC.

3.2 ESTIMATES PER TPTC

A record of all the potential sites is kept by TPTC, along with all the feasibility studies that have been performed. A total of thirty nine potential sites has been inventoried. These sites are summarized in Table 3-2, and in Exhibit A-5 (United Nations Industrial Development Organization, 2016). The estimated potential is 110,479 KW. One potential site not included in this list is the site of Dos Bocas. This site is located along the Haitian-Dominican border, and its capacity has been estimated at +/- 90 MW. Initial talk with the Dominican Republic resulted in a dead-end discussion since they were asking for 90% of the potential installed capacity. Besides, construction of the Dos-Bocas site will also result of the non-development of other sites along the River Guayamouc.

3.3 ESTIMATES PER WORLDWATCH INSTITUTE

In November 2014, the Worldwatch Institute published the "Haiti Sustainable Energy Roadmap" listing all the renewable energy sources that were available. One section was dedicated on the hydroelectric potential with data provided by SOLEO Energies. The data provided were based on 30 meters digital elevations model (DEM), and rainfall and evaporation data from weather stations of Haiti and the Dominican Republic. The flow data were estimated using a water balance approach and calibrated only for rivers having historical flow data. A total of 146 potential sites was identified, yielding a maximum potential of 345,148 KW and a maximum potential energy estimate of 2,360,925,120 KWH (Worldwatch Institute, 2014). This estimate was based on non-calibrated hydrology data. The general location of these sites is shown in Figure 1.

SITE ID	SITE NAME	DEPARTMENT	POTENTIAL CAPACITY (KW)	ANNUAL ENERGY (KWH)
HT001	Artibonite A109.1	Artibonite	20,936	113,700,000
HT002	Artibonite A139.9	Artibonite	28,600	155,300,000
HT003	Artibonite A4C	Centre	30,000	162,900,000
HT004	Bassin Bleu	Sud-Est	129	320,000
HT005	Bouyaha B11	Centre	630	4,300,000
HT006	Bouyaha B66.1	Nord	460	3,100,000
HT007	Caracol Modification	Nord	282	920,000
HT008	Cavaillon C42.3	Sud	240	1,300,000
HT009	Cazale 1	Ouest	890	2,900,000
HT010	Cazale 2	Ouest	470	1,700,000
HT011	Deluge-Lanzac	Artibonite	1,180	3,250,000
HT012	Fer a Cheval FC34.1	Centre	190	1,300,000
HT013	Fer a Cheval FC8.5	Centre	740	4,500,000
HT014	Gobe	Artibonite	190	730,000
HT015	Grande Anse BD8.6	Grande Anse	1,060	8,600,000
HT016	Grande Anse BG15.4	Grande Anse	2,480	20,200,000
HT017	Grande Anse GA35.4	Grande Anse	970	7,900,000
HT018	Grande Anse GA4.1	Grande Anse	1,210	9,800,000
HT019	Grande Riviere de Nippes GNIP29.5	Nippes	382	2,000,000
HT020	Grande Riviere du Nord GN30.3	Nord	720	4,900,000
HT021	Grande Riviere du Nord GN47.7	Nord-Est	480	3,200,000
HT022	Guayamouc GU25.7	Centre	2,134	14,200,000
HT023	Guayamouc GU3.5	Centre	3,408	7,400,000
HT024	La Gosseline	Sud-Est	153	360,000
HT025	La Theme LA1.6	Centre	1,349	10,600,000
HT026	Limbe L27.1	Nord	520	4,300,000
HT027	Limbe L33.7	Nord	360	2,900,000
HT028	Momance	Ouest	1,120	3,500,000
HT029	Petite Riviere	Nord	130	419,000
HT030	Pichon 1	Sud-Est	400	2,500,000
HT031	Pichon 2	Sud-Est	680	5,300,000
HT032	Riviere Grise G31.0	Ouest	720	5,900,000
HT033	Riviere Grise G41.1	Ouest	379	2,000,000
HT034	Roche Plate	Centre	2,570	9,810,000
HT035	Samana	Centre	776	2,520,000
HT036	Saut d'Eau	Centre	670	5,740,000
HT037	Saut du Baril	Nippes	365	1,230,000
HT038	Trois Rivieres TR28	Nord-Ouest	1,778	14,200,000
HT039	Trois Rivieres TR78	Artibonite	728	5,900,000

Table 3-2 Estimate of Haiti's hydropower potential per TPTC

Figure 1 General Hydroelectric Potential Map (SOLEO Energies 2011)

4 GIS BASED PROCEDURAL METHOD

A more comprehensive estimate of the potential has been achieved by using data, and softwares that were not available in the past. Nowadays there are a wealth of information that could be processed and analyzed to converge the estimate. This type of data processing is made possible with the use of GIS. Three main tasks are required to locate a potential hydroelectric site. These three tasks are:

- Data gathering
- Water balance procedure for flow estimation
- Hydraulic analysis procedure for power estimation

4.1 DATA GATHERING

The data needed to analyze a potential site are numerous. Some of the data are constant such as the terrain elevations by Light Detection and Ranging (LIDAR), others are temporal such as monthly rainfall and evaporation data. The data gathering flow chart is illustrated in Figure 2.

4.1.1 QUAD Maps

A set of revised geodetic maps first published in 1963 by the Defense Mapping Agency Hydrographic/Topographic Center. The scale of these maps is 1:50,000 and contour interval of 20 meters. These maps are useful in spotting perennial and seasonal rivers, waterfalls, dams, and other physical features that will exclude the possibility of planning a hydroelectric facility.

4.1.2 Aerial Maps

Aerial maps supplement the quad maps for locating new features not yet part of their updates. For this study three sets of aerial images were used. One set flown in January 2010 with a resolution of 30 centimeters that covers the south of Haiti, one set flown in April 2016 with a resolution of 25 centimeters that covers the entire country, and historical satellite images from Google Earth.

The historical satellite images from Google Earth show images at different months (rainy and dry season), and at different years. These images are very useful in filtering out seasonal rivers which might not have been identified properly in the quad maps.

4.1.3 LIDAR and DEM

An important set of data used to process elevations, stream networks, and watersheds delineation is either the LIDAR, or the DEM. The DEM used for this study is the 30 meters for Hispaniola provided by the Ministry of Economy, Trade, and Industry of Japan. This DEM was combined with the 1.50 meters LIDAR for Haiti provided by the "Centre National de l'Information Geo-Spatiale" (CNIGS). The 30 meters DEM, and the 1.50 meters LIDAR were combined in order to complete watersheds delineation for drainage basins extending beyond the Haitian-Dominican border.

Delineation of watersheds at prospective potential sites are performed by the "R.WATER.OUTLET" and "R.WATERSHED" plugins of Quantum GIS (QGIS). Once a watershed is delineated, other data processing and analysis are possible with the end result of estimating the monthly river flow for a potential site. Other data that are extracted from the LIDAR are the dam and powerhouse setting elevation which will be used to estimate the gross head, and eventually the power estimation of a site. The 1.50 meters LIDAR has proved to be an invaluable tool in evaluating the hydroelectric potential of Haiti.

Figure 2 Data Gathering Flow Chart

4.1.4 Soils Maps

The Food and Agricultural Organization of the United Nations (FAO) has published soils classification data of the world (FAO-UNESCO, 1975). The database lists the soil number, soil code, soil name, and soil potential water storage in millimeter. Additional references have been researched to find the equivalencies of the soils with the Hydrologic Soil Group per the Soil Conservation Survey (SCS) of the United States Department of Agriculture. There are four types of Hydrologic Soil Group listed as A, B, C, and D.

- Soil group A is characterized by soils having low runoff potential and high infiltration rates even when thoroughly wetted; consist chiefly of deep, well to excessively drained sands or gravels.
- Soil group B is characterized by soils having moderate infiltration rate and consist of soil chiefly with moderately fine to moderately coarse textures.
- Soil group C is characterized by soils having low infiltration rates when thoroughly wetted and consist chiefly of soils with moderately fine to fine structure.
- Soil group D is characterized by soils having highest runoff potential, very low infiltration rates when thoroughly wetted and consist chiefly of clay soils.

For the island of Hispaniola there are fifteen predominant types of soils as shown in Table 4-1 below, and in Exhibit A-1. The soils water storage capacity, and the soils hydrologic group are two important parameters that affect a stream flow.

SOIL CODE	SOIL NAME	SOIL WATER STORAGE CAPACITY (mm)	SCS HYDROLOGIC SOIL GROUP
Ao	Orthic Acrisol	425	B
Be	Eutric Cambisol	255	B
Fa	Acric Ferralsol	782	D
I	Lithosol	17	D
Je	Eutric Fluvisol	340	B
Lc	Chromic Luvisol	212	B
Nd	Dystric Nitosol	323	B
Vp	Pellic Vertisol	289	D
We	Eutric Planosol	255	D
Ne	Eutric Nitosol	425	B
Gm	Mollic Gleisol	612	D
Bc	Chromic Cambisol	224	B
WR	Water Bodies	0	D
Bd	Dystric Cambisol	224	B
Lo	Orthic Luvisol	285	B
Ao	Orthic Acrisol	425	B

Table 4-1 Major Soils Classification and Hydrologic Soil Group for Hispaniola

4.1.5 Land Use and Land Cover Maps

Complementary to the soils data, are the land use and land cover data. The land use and land cover data along with the type of soils have an effect on the surface runoff as well as on the

underground flow to a river. The land use and land cover type data are based on ten years of collection (2001-2010) with an accuracy of 500 meters grid. These data are known as Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS). Access to the MODIS data for Hispaniola is from the website of the United States National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA). The correlation between the MODIS land cover classification and the surface runoff is achieved through the SCS curve number (CN). The CN values relate to the SCS hydrologic soil group. The table below relates the correlation between the MODIS land cover classification and the CN values from the SCS hydrologic soil group (Unknown & Said, 2003) (Benedict Mwavu, April 2007).

MODIS	LAND COVER CLASSIFICATION	CN FOR DIFFERENT HYDROLOGIC SOIL GROUP			
ID	CONTENT	A	B	C	D
0	Water bodies	100	100	100	100
1	Evergreen needles	34	60	73	79
2	Evergreen broadleaf	30	58	71	77
3	Deciduous needle leaf	40	64	77	83
4	Deciduous broadleaf	42	66	79	85
5	Mixed forests	38	62	75	81
6	Closed shrublands	45	65	75	80
7	Open shrublands	49	69	79	84
8	Woody savannas	61	71	81	89
9	Savannas	72	80	87	93
10	Grasslands	49	69	79	84
11	Permanent wetlands	30	58	71	78
12	Croplands	67	78	85	89
13	Urban and built-up	80	85	90	95
14	Cropland/natural vegetation mosaic	52	69	79	84
15	Permanent snow and ice	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
16	Barren or sparsely vegetated	72	82	83	87
17	Missing data	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

Table 4-2 Correlation between MODIS Land Cover Classification and Curve Number CN

The soils data, and the land use data are joined. The values/descriptions are filtered, and CN values are populated based on the criteria of Table 4-1, and Table 4-2. The limits of each MODIS land cover classification are shown in Exhibit A-2.

4.1.6 Historical Flow Data

A number of rivers have daily historical flow data for a number of years. Of the thirty three major rivers identified, twenty six of these have gauging flow data gathered at twenty nine stations (Lalonde, Girouard, Letendre & Associates, 1977). These daily flow data are important for calibration of flow model for rivers where no flow is available. The table below lists the gauging station identification, the river name, and the location of the selected gauging stations. The geographical location as well as the hydrologic data of these gauging sites are displayed in Exhibits C-1 through C-30.

STATION ID	STATION RIVER	STATION LOCATION
010501	Grande Riviere du Nord	Pont Parois
020111	Riviere d'Ennery	Passe Joly
020701	Riviere Trois Rivieres	Plaisance
020702	Riviere Trois Rivieres	Plaisance
020703	Riviere Trois Rivieres	Plaisance
030101	Riviere de Montrouis	Pont Toussaint
030201	Riviere de l'Artibonite	Pont Sonde
030202	Riviere de l'Artibonite	Mirebalais
030211	Riviere Bois	Verrettes
030221	Riviere la Theme	Passe Fine
030231	Riviere Fer a Cheval	Pont Petion
030241	Riviere Onde Verte	Onde Verte
030251	Riviere Guayamouc	Hinche
030252	Riviere Bouyaha	Saint-Raphael
030404	Riviere Saint Marc	Corbay
040201	Riviere Momance	Bussonniere
040501	Riviere Grise	Amont Du Basin
040601	Riviere Blanche	La Gorge
040801	Riviere Torcelle	Messaye
040901	Riviere Coujol	Bassin Proby
041001	Riviere des Matheux	Arcahaie
050201	Riviere Jacmel	Jacmel
050401	Riviere Marigot	Marigot
060501	Ravine du Sud	Camp Perrin
060601	Riviere Cavaillon	Cavaillon
060801	Riviere Cotes de Fer	Cotes De Fer
070201	Riviere Voldroque	Passe Laraque
070301	Riviere Grande Anse	Passe Ranja
099999	Riviere de l'Artibonite	Peligre

Table 4-3 Existing Gauging Stations List

4.1.7 Monthly Rainfall and Evaporation Data

The island of Hispaniola is blessed with ample rainfall that stretches over two rainy seasons. Many areas receive rains in excess of 2,000 millimeters a year. In the south, the Saut-Mathurine region receives rains in excess of 4,000 millimeters a year. Typically, the rainy season starts early and ends late in the mountainous areas. Scattered all over the island are 157 weather stations having rainfall, and evapotranspiration data ranging from a few year years to over fifty years (Lalonde, Girouard, Letendre & Associates, 1977) (Hargreaves & Samani, 1986). However, most of these stations are located along the coast, and the data collected do not fully represent the rainfall depth at locations that are a few miles inland and at higher elevations where the rainfall depth are typically more. To supplement at this lack of data and spatial coverage, rainfall and evapotranspiration data in raster format were obtained from FAO (FAO, 2014). These raster data

are available for every months of the year from 1901 to 2011. The geographical locations of the weather stations are displayed in Exhibit B-1. Average annual, and average monthly of the rainfall and evapotranspiration depth are displayed in Exhibit B-2 to B-27.

4.1.8 Hydrography

Haiti is a mountainous country with favorable climatic conditions characterized by two rainy seasons. The country has five mountain ranges that are drained by many rivers and streams. There are thirty three major rivers which in turn branch out into multiple streams. This study has identified more than 200 streams that form the hydrographic network of the country. The majority of these streams have little or no water during the dry season. Although the vast majority of these streams have been identified in the available quad maps, many are not shown, or are improperly drawn as perennial instead of intermittent. The historical images of Google Earth have been used to reclassify these streams.

4.1.9 Known Waterfalls

There are many waterfalls located along the main rivers and streams. Although the vast majority are not geographically located on the geodetic maps, many localities with the name "Saut" suggest the presence of a waterfall. With the use of the filtering capability of GIS, these localities were highlighted for further exploration from aerial photographs.

Figure 3 Waterfalls along Head-Water of River Gosseline (Source: Ministry of Tourism)

4.1.10 Geology

Haiti is crisscrossed by many fault lines. One such fault line is the “Enriquillo” fault line that divides the southern peninsula between the Caribbean Plate, and the Gonave Microplate. The major fault lines of Hispaniola are illustrated in figure 4.

Figure 4 Hispaniola Major Fault Lines (Source: WIKIPEDIA.ORG)

Along the “Enriquillo” fault line there are a number of major rivers that follow this fault line. From west to east we encounter the following rivers:

- Riviere Les Irois
- Riviere Les Anglais
- Ravine du Sud
- Riviere Cavaillon
- Grande Riviere de Nippes
- Riviere Momance
- Riviere Froide

The occurrence of a fault line typically excludes the setting of gravity dams with major impoundments. For this study, any proposed gravity dam within a fault line has been changed to a Tyrolean dam with no impoundment. A GIS layer that shows all the major fault lines, and minor fault lines has been used to perform the filtering for the type of dams.

4.2 WATER BALANCE PROCEDURE

The vast majority of the rivers in Haiti have no flow gauging information. As mentioned before, of the thirty three major rivers identified, twenty six of these have gauging flow data gathered at twenty nine stations (Lalonde, Girouard, Letendre & Associates, 1977). Other rivers have only scanty flow measurements for one event. All of these flow measurements are at location that usually are not corresponding to potential hydropower sites.

To estimate river flow at ungauged sites a handful of hydrologic methods can be used. The most common is the flow area method by either interpolating or extrapolating the flow data based on the tributary watershed area. This method is only accurate for watersheds having similar climatic conditions, land use, and soils as the referenced watershed. Such similarities are scarce.

Another method that is well adapted to the GIS platform is the “Water Balance” method. The water balance method uses precipitation and evapotranspiration data, and the existing soil storage capacity to calculate daily or monthly streamflow. Satisfactory results of the streamflow can be achieved by calibrating the results obtained by the water balance method with a few discharge measurements. This method has been used to estimate the flow of the potential hydropower sites of this study.

4.2.1 Description

The water balance method used in this study is based on monthly lumped rainfall-runoff method that was first proposed by Crawford and Thurin (Crawford & Thurin, 1981), and later modified to a daily time step by Reichl and Hack (Reichl & Hack, 2017). These two variances of the water balance method have been modified to include variation of the SCS CN number for different hydrologic soil group, land cover type, and seasonal changes of the soil antecedent moisture condition. An excel macro numerical program has been written to first calibrate a yearly synthetic river flow hydrograph with the twenty six river flow hydrographs available, and finally utilized the calibrated factors to estimate the yearly hydrograph at ungauged sites.

The basic equation for the water balance method is:

$$P = AET + RUNOFF + DFLOW + GWLOSS + BFLOW1 + (BFLOW2) + \Delta S$$

With,

P	Precipitation (mm)
AET	Actual evapotranspiration (mm)
PET	Potential evapotranspiration (mm)
RUNOFF	Surface runoff (SCS) to stream (mm)
DFLOW	Direct flow to stream (mm)
GWLOSS	Flow loss to groundwater (mm)
BFLOW1	Base flow from within watershed (mm)
BFLOW2	Base flow from outside watershed – for calibration only (mm)
ΔS	Change in groundwater storage (mm)

The basic overview of the model structure is illustrated in figure 5.

Figure 5 Water Balance equation illustration

The model uses six parameters which are estimated and calibrated for each referenced watershed where gauging data are available. These parameters are RFLK, PSUB, GWF, GWL, BFLK, and NOMINAL.

RFLK is a fraction of the surface runoff that flows directly to the stream.

PSUB is a fraction of the remaining surface runoff from above that reach the groundwater layer. PSUB could be estimated as follow:

- PSUB = 0.8 for watershed with high soil permeability
- PSUB = 0.3 for watershed with low soil permeability or thin soil

GWF is a fraction of groundwater flowing to the stream. GWF could be estimated as follow:

- GWF = 0.9 for watershed with little sustained flow
- GWF = 0.2 for watershed with reliable sustained flow

GWL is a fraction of the groundwater flowing out of the watershed.

BFLK is an amount of deep groundwater flow outside of the watershed that is contributing to the stream flow. This variable is not derived from the hydrological data (precipitation, and potential evapotranspiration), it is a variable used to calibrate the stream base flow from gauging data.

NOMINAL is the soil storage capacity for the type of soil. In the model NOMINAL is set initially as the maximum soil storage capacity as to the type of soil (Table 4-1). After many iterations

(typically five years of simulation) the monthly value for NOMINAL converge. This approach is different than the one proposed by Crawford and Thurin where NOMINAL is estimated by:

$$NOMINAL = 100 + C * Mean Annual Precipitation$$

Where C varies between 0.20 for watersheds having rainfall event occurring throughout the year, and 0.25 for watershed having seasonal rainfall.

The excel macro analysis follows these steps.

Step 1: Surface runoff

The surface runoff (RUNOFF) is estimated by the following equation:

$$RUNOFF = RFLK * \frac{(P - 0.2S)^2}{(P + 0.8S)}$$

With,

P Precipitation (mm).
S Soil storage (mm) defined by:

$$S = \frac{25,400}{CN} - 254CN$$

With,

CN SCS curve number that varies based on the antecedent soil moisture condition.

For dry moisture condition (I) when (P/PET) < 0.8, CN is calculated by:

$$CN(I) = \frac{4.2 CN(II)}{10 - 0.058CN(II)}$$

For normal moisture condition (II) when 0.8 ≤ (P/PET) ≤ 0.9, CN is calculated by:

$$CN(II) = CN$$

For wet moisture condition (III) when (P/PET) ≥ 0.9, CN is calculated by:

$$CN(III) = \frac{23 CN(II)}{10 + 0.13CN(II)}$$

The model adjusts the curve number CN (Chow, 1988) based on the ratio of P/PET which defined the dry or wet season. The factor RFLK determines the amount of surface runoff flowing directly to the stream.

Step 2: Actual evapotranspiration

The actual evapotranspiration (AET) is the actual water loss which is less or equal to the potential evapotranspiration. The actual evapotranspiration is a function of the soil moisture storage ratio and the ratio of the precipitation over the potential evapotranspiration. The procedure to calculate AET is as proposed by Crawford and Thurin (Crawford & Thurin, 1981).

First the excess moisture ratio (STORAT) at a given time is calculated as a ratio of the initial soil moisture storage over the overall soil storage capacity (NOMINAL). It is given by:

$$STORAT = \frac{SOIL\ MOISTURE\ STORAGE}{NOMINAL}$$

Next the soil moisture ratio (SMSR) is estimated from figure 6 or the following equation:

$$SMSR = 0.5 * STORAT^2 \quad \text{for } STORAT < 1$$

And

$$SMSR = 1 - (0.5 * (2 - STORAT))^2 \quad \text{for } STORAT \geq 1$$

Figure 6 Soil Moisture Storage Ratio / Excess moisture ratio

The ratio of the actual evapotranspiration over the potential evapotranspiration (AET/PET) is then estimated from figure 7 or the following equation:

$$\frac{AET}{PET} = \frac{SMSR}{2} + \left(1 - \frac{SMSR}{2}\right) * \frac{(P - RUNOFF)}{PET}$$

The actual evapotranspiration is then calculated by multiplying the AET/PET ratio from above with potential evapotranspiration (PET) at a given time.

Figure 7 (AET/PET) as function of (P/PET) and soil moisture storage ratio (SMSR)

Step 3: Water balance

At the end of the time interval, the water balance (WATBAL) is calculated as the difference between the precipitation and the actual evapotranspiration.

$$WATBAL = P - AET$$

Step 4: Soil Excess Moisture

The soil excess moisture (EXMST) is calculated by:

$$EXMST = SMSR * WATBAL$$

Step 5: Change in soil water storage

The change in soil water storage is calculated by:

$$\Delta S = WATBAL - EXMST$$

Step 6: Groundwater recharge

As the deep layer of soil (below the surficial layer) receives more water, portion of it recharges that soil layer first. The groundwater recharge is calculated by:

$$GWRECH = PSUB * EXMST$$

Which is added to the time step initial soil ground water storage (GWSTORE).

$$GWSTORE = GWSTORE + GWRECH$$

Step 7: Direct flow to the stream

Once the deep layer of soil is saturated, the excess water flows directly to the stream. The direct flow (DFLOW) to the stream is calculated by:

$$DFLOW = EXMST - GWRECH$$

Step 8: Groundwater loss

Portion of the groundwater stored in the saturated soil might flow out of the watershed and is accounted for as loss. This groundwater loss (GWLOSS) is calculated by:

$$GWLOSS = GWSTORE * GWL$$

Step 9: Base flow

Portion of the stream flow that is sustained between precipitation events is called base flow, or groundwater recession flow. Crawford and Thurin (Crawford & Thurin, 1981) proposed a constant factor (GWF) applied to the groundwater storage to estimate the base flow. This approach was used at first but calibration of the synthetic yearly hydrograph with any given yearly hydrograph was not achieved. This approach was modified to account for the variation in precipitation between each rainy and dry season. A variable that proves to give acceptable result is the ratio of the actual evapotranspiration over the potential evapotranspiration (AET/PET). The base flow (BASEFLOW1) is calculated by:

$$BASEFLOW1 = GWSTORE * GWF * \left(\frac{AET}{PET} \right)$$

Another base flow that was added to the model is the contribution of deep groundwater flow. In performing the water balance analysis using available precipitation and potential evapotranspiration data, it became evident that the record of flows was higher than what could be obtained from these data. It could be years before this deep groundwater flow will get

depleted, possibly being replenished by extraordinary rainfall event such as hurricanes. This type of flow (BASEFLOW2) is calculated by:

$$BASEFLOW2 = BFLK * \left(\frac{AET}{PET}\right)$$

The separation between the river flow and the base flow is illustrated in figure 8.

Figure 8 Separation between river flow and base flow

The flow to the river is the summation of all the flows.

$$FLOW = RUNOFF + DFLOW + BASEFLOW1 + BASEFLOW2$$

At the end of this time step, the calculation will proceed to the next time step until the end of the year is reached. This process is repeated until the initial value for NOMINAL converges, meaning there is no flow values difference for one year to the next. Typically, convergence is achieved after five years of simulation.

A sample of the results from the calculations performed is displayed in Table 4-4 below.

(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)=(2)-(10)	(12)	(13)	(14)	(15)=PSUB*(13)	(16)	(17)=(17)+(15)	(18)=GWL*(17)	(19)=GWF*(17)	(20)=(17)-(18)-(19)	(17)-(13)-(15)	(22)=BFLK*(9)	(23)=(6)+(19)+(17)+(22)	(24)	(25)
Month	P	PET	Begin Moist Storage	Curve Number	Rainfall Excess	Storage Ratio	P/PET	AET/PET	AET	Water Balance	Excess Moist Ratio	Excess Moist	Delta Storage	Recharge to GW	End Moist Storage	Begin Storage GW	GW Loss	GW Flow	End Storage GW	Direct Flow	Base Flow	Total Discharge	Average Flow	Average Flow
	mm	mm	mm		mm				mm	mm		mm	mm	mm	mm	mm	mm	mm	mm	mm	mm	mm	m ³ /s	ft ³ /s
January	29.39	113.43	38.29	51.68	0.00	0.29	0.26	0.37	41.62	-12.23	0.00	0.00	-12.23	0.00	26.06	2.63	0.00	0.14	2.49	0.00	5.19	5.32	13.3129	470.141
February	37.39	118.30	26.06	51.68	0.00	0.20	0.32	0.38	45.40	-8.01	0.00	0.00	-8.01	0.00	18.04	2.49	0.00	0.16	2.33	0.00	6.33	6.48	17.9556	634.096
March	51.40	153.99	18.04	51.68	0.02	0.14	0.33	0.38	58.42	-7.02	0.00	0.00	-7.02	0.00	11.01	2.33	0.00	0.16	2.18	0.00	6.68	6.85	17.1349	605.113
April	125.96	157.51	11.01	51.68	4.80	0.08	0.77	0.78	122.68	3.28	0.00	0.01	3.27	0.01	9.47	2.19	0.00	0.34	1.85	0.00	15.39	20.54	53.0879	1874.780
May	237.96	162.20	9.47	85.41	47.54	0.07	1.17	1.00	162.20	75.76	0.00	0.20	75.56	0.16	37.49	2.01	0.00	0.47	1.54	0.04	23.49	71.55	178.9965	6321.201
June	182.53	160.14	37.49	85.41	34.31	0.29	0.93	0.94	149.92	32.61	0.04	1.32	31.29	1.06	34.47	2.60	0.00	0.48	2.11	0.26	18.52	53.58	138.5079	4891.360
July	140.08	171.18	34.47	71.80	16.18	0.26	0.72	0.76	130.09	9.99	0.03	0.34	9.64	0.27	27.93	2.39	0.00	0.35	2.04	0.07	14.48	31.08	77.7594	2746.046
August	177.33	167.97	27.93	85.41	33.08	0.21	0.86	0.87	146.77	30.56	0.02	0.69	29.87	0.55	24.72	2.59	0.00	0.45	2.15	0.14	17.19	50.85	127.2144	4492.534
September	207.32	151.16	24.72	85.41	40.20	0.19	1.11	1.00	151.16	56.16	0.02	0.99	55.17	0.79	39.69	2.94	0.00	0.65	2.29	0.20	22.13	63.18	163.3249	5767.764
October	187.18	133.84	39.69	85.41	35.41	0.30	1.13	1.00	133.84	53.34	0.05	2.43	50.91	1.94	55.19	4.23	0.00	0.96	3.27	0.49	22.69	59.55	148.9824	5261.263
November	91.43	111.28	55.19	71.80	7.36	0.42	0.76	0.81	89.78	1.65	0.09	0.15	1.50	0.12	49.34	3.39	0.00	0.51	2.88	0.03	15.12	23.02	59.5053	2101.411
December	45.94	104.86	49.34	51.68	0.00	0.38	0.44	0.54	56.99	-11.05	0.00	0.00	-11.05	0.00	38.29	2.88	0.00	0.25	2.63	0.00	8.77	9.02	22.5656	796.897

Table 4-4 Sample water balance tabular calculation of monthly runoff

4.2.2 Calibration

The variables RFLK, PSUB, GWF, GWL, BFLK, and NOMINAL are adjusted for the modeled stream flow to match the historical river gauging records. As mentioned before, of the thirty three major rivers identified, twenty six of these have gauging flow data gathered at twenty nine stations (Lalonde, Girouard, Letendre & Associates, 1977). For each of these stations the variables have been adjusted until a close fit has been achieved between the modeled and historical stream hydrograph. Consequently, for any potential hydro site located within a gauged watershed, or within an area having similar watershed characteristics, will share the same calibration variables. Similar watershed characteristics will include watersheds with same hydrological conditions, moderate changes in soils, land use, vegetation, elevation, and subsurface hydrology. Typically, the model achieved a goodness of fit of around 85% between the synthetic and historical river flow hydrograph. A sample hydrograph comparing the historical and modeled flow is shown in figure 9.

Figure 9 Synthetic river flow hydrograph – comparison with historical flow

4.3 HYDRAULIC ANALYSIS PROCEDURE

An excel macro has been written to perform the hydraulic analysis of a potential hydroelectric site. This analysis is general in nature and does not replace a detail engineering calculation of the various components that are required to estimate the potential power or energy capacity of a site. However, every hydroelectric site shares some mutual components such as the dam, the reservoir, the penstock, and the turbine. The macro written for this Potential Mapping Atlas uses data supplied through the GIS platform to analyze each site. For the purpose of this study many simplifications have been inserted in the excel macro but to conservatively achieve a reasonable estimate of the potential.

4.3.1 Hydraulic Components

Typically, a hydroelectric power plant is defined by a dam, a reservoir, a channel, a penstock, and a turbine. Other ancillary structures are the settling basin, and the forebay tank. These components are illustrated in figure 10.

Figure 10 Typical components of a hydropower facility (run-of-river)

4.3.1.1 Dam

For this study two types of dams have been used. There are either a standard gravity dam, or a Tyrolean dam.

The gravity and Tyrolean dam are defined by the followings:

- Riverbed elevation at dam setting
- Water surface control elevation

The riverbed elevation is extracted automatically from the 1.50 meters LIDAR. The dam height neglecting freeboard is the difference between the water surface control elevation and the riverbed elevation at dam setting. For Tyrolean dam the default height is 2 meters.

4.3.1.2 Reservoir

The analysis of a potential site is performed using a simple reservoir that is defined by an average top area at the given water surface control elevation, and an average storage height which is defaulted as 1/3 of the dam height. The average reservoir top area is delineated in QGIS by using the "R.LAKE" plugin, and the 1.50 meters LIDAR. For the gravity dam system, the reservoir storage volume is the product of the reservoir average top area by the average storage height. For Tyrolean dam system, no storage volume is accounted for.

The reservoir storage volume will supply additional flow to supplement the river flow when it is less than the turbine design flow. This additional flow is calculated by dividing the reservoir volume over the amount of time the river flow is less than the turbine design flow.

4.3.1.3 Settling basin

Directly after the dam, and typical for run-of-the river installation (Figure 10), a settling tank is usually provided. It is basically a wide channel that decrease the water velocity to allow sediments to settle. In this study the location and preliminary sizing of settling basins has not been performed since it is an ancillary structure that is usually designed for detailed engineering study. Neglecting the head loss through this structure in the general evaluation of the power estimate is minimal.

4.3.1.4 Headway canal or channel

The headway canal links the settling basin to the forebay tank. The headway canal is sloped longitudinally to provide self-cleaning velocity of sediments that could bypass the settling tank, thus avoiding the sediments from being deposited in the channel. In this study a self-cleaning velocity of 0.60 m/s has been set as default value. The channel slope needed to achieve this velocity is given by the manning equation:

$$S = \left(\frac{V * n}{R_h^{2/3}} \right)^2$$

With,

- S channel slope in m/m.
- V channel velocity defaulted to 0.60 m/s.
- n channel manning coefficient defaulted to 0.016 typical for concrete lining.
- R_h hydraulic radius defined as the quotient of the flow area over the wet perimeter.

This slope is the minimum slope needed to achieve the self-cleansing velocity and is also the slope of the hydraulic grade line. The slope times the length of the channel will give the head loss from begin to end of the channel.

The length of the channel is estimated in this study from the map distance between the dam and the hydropower station setting. To account for the sinuosity of the terrain, which is typical of the mountainous area of Haiti, the length of the canal is estimated by:

$$L_{canal} = 3 * (1.75 L_{map})$$

With,

L_{map} straight line map distance between the dam and the station.

The value for the channel length for each site is populated by linking the GIS output with the excel-macro written for this study.

For the case of gravity dam with reservoir, no channel is provided.

4.3.1.5 Forebay tank

The forebay tank is a terminal structure that is used to connect the channel with the penstock. It is usually fitted with trash rack to prevent debris from being sucked into the penstock. It has also a sump to collect coarse sediments that could have fallen into the channel. The forebay needs to provide the proper submergence over the crown of the penstock pipe to prevent the formation of vortex that will entrain air inside the penstock. A spillway is usually provided as a way to regulate the water level in the forebay tank. This ancillary structure is typically a component of run-of-the river facilities. In this study the location and preliminary sizing of forebay tanks has not been performed since it is an ancillary structure that is usually designed for detailed engineering study. Neglecting the head loss through this structure in the general evaluation of the power estimate is minimal.

4.3.1.6 Penstock

A penstock is a closed conduit or pressure pipe that supplies water under pressure from the forebay tank to the turbine. The maximum velocity has been limited to 6 m/s and the maximum head loss to 15% of the gross head. Another analysis assumption is the use of one single penstock supplying flow to either one turbine, or many turbines up to a maximum of four. The hydraulic grade line minimum slope is given by the manning equation. The manning equation is used for its simplicity, a more appropriate formula for pressure flow in pipe is the Darcy-Weisbach.

$$S = \left(\frac{(Q/A) * n}{R_h^{2/3}} \right)^2$$

With,

- S penstock hydraulic grade line slope in m/m.
- Q the turbine flow in m³/s.
- A the cross sectional area of the penstock in m²
- n penstock manning coefficient defaulted to 0.012
- R_h hydraulic radius defined as the quotient of the flow area over the wet perimeter

The slope times the length of the penstock will give the head loss from begin to end of the penstock.

The length of the penstock is estimated in this study from the map distance between the dam and the hydropower station setting. To account for the sinuosity of the terrain, which is typical of the mountainous area of Haiti, the length of the penstock is estimated by:

$$L_{penstock} = 6 * (1.75 L_{map})$$

With,

L_{map} straight line map distance between the dam and the station

The value for the penstock length for each site is populated by linking the GIS output with the excel-macro written for this study. For the estimation of the head loss analysis through fittings, the number of fittings has been laid on a spacing of 200 meters along the penstock length.

4.3.1.7 Turbine

A turbine is a mechanical device that extract the energy of flowing water to convert it to energy. Turbines are either classified as reaction or impulse. For impulse turbine, the pressure of the fluid does not change while flowing through the rotating wheel. For reaction turbine, the major portion of the pressure drop occurs in the rotating wheel. There are five types of turbines, each with their applicability range for the flow and head. The applicability range used in this study has been adapted from many sources and is summarized in table 4-5 below.

TURBINE TYPE	MINIMUM FLOW RANGE (m ³ /s)	MAXIMUM FLOW RANGE (m ³ /s)	MINIMUM HEAD (m)	MAXIMUM HEAD (m)	OPTIMUM FLOW EXCEEDENCE (%)	RATIO MINIMUM FLOW TO DESIGN FLOW (%)
Cross-Flow	0.05	10.00	2.00	200.00	10	33
Francis	0.50	900.00	10.00	400.00	25	40
Pelton	0.01	60.00	50.00	1000.00	10	20
Turgo	0.01	10.00	50.00	500.00	20	20
Kaplan	0.50	50.00	4.00	100.00	15	35

Table 4-5 Applicability range of various turbines

For a given site many different turbines can be used if within the range of applicability. The range of applicability is pictorially represented in figure 11. This figure was created by using the range of applicability from different sources.

Figure 11 Turbine selection chart (adapted from many sources)

Each turbine type is also characterized by its efficiency. The efficiency in general depends on the ratio of available flow with the turbine design flow. Generic type equation for each turbine is given by (Fritz, 1984):

Cross-Flow turbine

$$ET = -0.27946 + (13.068 * A) - (81.222 * A^2) + (275.787 * A^3) - (534.982 * A^4) + (592.367 * A^5) - (348.08 * A^6) + (84.1433 * A^7)$$

Francis turbine

$$ET = -1.38959 + (17.6433 * A) - (70.5159 * A^2) + (174.261 * A^3) - (273.511 * A^4) + (266.656 * A^5) - (146.992 * A^6) + (34.6991 * A^7)$$

Pelton turbine

$$ET = 0.00714 + (11.0712 * A) - (63.874 * A^2) + (207.119 * A^3) - (396.07 * A^4) + (440.759 * A^5) - (262.98 * A^6) + (64.8347 * A^7)$$

Turgo turbine

$$ET = 0.131789 + (6.86047 * A) - (35.21 * A^2) + (105.665 * A^3) - (186.658 * A^4) + (191.065 * A^5) - (104.956 * A^6) + (23.9621 * A^7)$$

Kaplan turbine

$$ET = -0.157845 + (5.16567 * A) - (12.5331 * A^2) + (18.6549 * A^3) - (16.1621 * A^4) + (6.06582 * A^5) + (0.91835 * A^6) - (1.05123 * A^7)$$

With,

ET turbine efficiency

A ratio of river flow or penstock flow over the turbine rated flow

In this study for each potential site, the setting of a site turbine considered the turbine applicability, best efficiency, and maximum energy production over the daily flow fluctuation. The analysis also evaluates the need of having one of more turbines and up to four to improve the overall plant efficiency.at low flow, or to limit the size of the turbine for rivers that have high flows. A representation of each turbine type is shown in Appendix F.

Typical Cross-flow generic efficiency curves for one turbine and up to four turbines working in parallel through one common penstock is represented in figure 12 (Retscreen, 2001-2004).

Figure 12 Typical generic efficiency curves for Cross-flow turbine

Typical Francis generic efficiency curves for one turbine and up to four turbines working in parallel through one common penstock is represented in figure 13 (Retscreen, 2001-2004).

Figure 13 Typical generic efficiency curves for Francis turbine

Typical Pelton generic efficiency curves for one turbine and up to four turbines working in parallel through one common penstock is represented in figure 14 (Retscreen, 2001-2004).

Figure 14 Typical generic efficiency curves for Pelton turbine

Typical Turgo generic efficiency curves for one turbine and up to four turbines working in parallel through one common penstock is represented in figure 15 (Retscreen, 2001-2004).

Figure 15 Typical generic efficiency curves for Turgo turbine

Typical Kaplan generic efficiency curves for one turbine and up to four turbines working in parallel through one common penstock is represented in figure 13 (Retscreen, 2001-2004).

Figure 16 Typical generic efficiency curves for Kaplan turbine

4.3.2 Potential Power and Energy

Once the hydrology of a potential site at dam setting has been determined, it is customary to rank specific river flows between its minimum and maximum value for the amount of time in percent they are exceeded. Once this ranking has been established, a turbine flow can be set which will be used to size the penstock and evaluate the power potential of a potential site.

4.3.2.1 Flow exceedance curve

The flow exceedance curve gives an overview of a potential site available river flow between its minimum and maximum value. The flow exceedance curve allows long term continuous simulation of the potential energy that could be produced. In this study, for each potential site a flow exceedance curve is created based on the modelled daily stream flow. A typical flow exceedance curve is represented in figure 17.

Figure 17 Typical percent exceedance curve

4.3.2.2 Turbine design flow

The turbine flow is limited by the upper limit of the river maximum flow, and the lower limit of the river minimum flow. Every type of turbine has a specific flow where its maximum efficiency is best achieved. The limiting factors in setting a turbine designed flow (operating point) has been described earlier in table 4-5 "Applicability range of various turbines". The variability of setting up a turbine designed flow is given by the following steps:

Step 1 – Set ranges of river flows.

$River_Flow_Min = Minimum\ River\ Flow$

$River_Flow_Max = Maximum\ River\ Flow$

Step 2 – Set turbine design flow.

$Design_Flow = Turbine\ Design\ Flow\ sets\ from\ Table\ 4-5\ and\ percent\ exceedance\ curve$

Step 3 – Set penstock flow.

$Pipe_Flow = Design_Flow$

Step 4 – Set maximum controlling flow.

- Case when $Pipe_Flow \leq River_Flow_Max$

$QMax = Pipe_Flow$

- Case when $Pipe_Flow > River_Flow_Max$

$QMax = River_Flow_Max$

Step 5 – Set turbine(s) unit flow.

$Turbine_Flow = (QMax * 3) / (2 * Nturbine + 1)$

With,

$Nturbine$ the number of turbines needed for the ratio of the minimum river flow over the turbine flow to be greater than the minimum value listed in table 4-5.

4.3.2.3 Water to wire plant efficiency

A hydroelectric power plant is characterized by its overall efficiency that is more commonly referred to as the water to wire efficiency. Typical water to wire efficiency varies from around 65% to 75% which is most of the time an optimum value related to the cost of an installation. The water to wire efficiency is given by the following equation:

$$E = E_P * E_T * E_G * E_L$$

With,

E_P the canal-penstock efficiency

E_T the turbine efficiency previously defined

E_G the generator efficiency defaulted to 98%

E_L the transmission line efficiency defaulted to 99%

From the head water surface elevation at the dam to the tail water elevation at turbine setting, losses occur first in the canal and then in the penstock. In this study assumptions were made to globally calculate the losses through a penstock. The losses through the penstock include entrance loss, bends loss, valve loss, pipe loss, and exit loss. The losses through the canal and the penstock are given by the following equation:

$$H_L = \frac{V^2}{2G} \left(K_1 + NB * K_2 + K_3 + K_4 + \frac{L_{penstock} * 19.613 * n^2}{R_H^{4/3}} \right) + L_{canal} * S$$

With,

- V the penstock velocity limited to 6 m/s
- G the earth gravity
- $K1$ the penstock entrance loss coefficient defaulted to 0.04 typical for bell mouth entrance
- NB the number of bends along the penstock at a defaulted spacing of 200 meters
- $K2$ the penstock loss coefficient for bend having a deflection angle of 15 degrees
- $K3$ the loss coefficient for one gate valve defaulted to 0.17
- $K4$ the penstock exit loss coefficient defaulted to 1.00

The variables $L_{penstock}$, L_{canal} , n , S , and R_h were previously defined.

The bend loss coefficient is estimated by the following equation:

$$K2 = 0.25 * \sqrt{\frac{\emptyset}{90}}$$

With,

- \emptyset the deflection angle at a bend defaulted to 15 degrees in the visual basic macro

The summation of canal loss and penstock loss give the overall loss of head. The canal-penstock efficiency is given by the following equation:

$$E_p = \frac{H_{GROSS} - H_L}{H_{GROSS}}$$

With

- H_{GROSS} the gross head defined as the maximum head difference between the elevation at the dam and the turbine setting elevation expressed in meter.

4.3.2.4 Potential power estimation

The potential power from a site is calculated from the available daily and monthly flows to create a yearly power duration curve. The power output is expressed by the following equation:

$$P = \rho * G * Q * H_{GROSS} * E$$

With,

- P the power output in KW
- ρ the water density defaulted to 1,000 kg/m³
- G the approximate value of gravity acceleration in m/sec²
- Q the turbine flow as it varies with the time of the year in m³/sec
- H_{GROSS} the gross head in meter
- E the overall efficiency

A sample power duration graph is represented in figure 18.

Figure 18 Sample monthly power duration graph

From the power duration graph the electric energy generated by continuous generation for a time duration can be estimated. The energy generated is expressed by kilowatt hour (KWH). The visual basic macro written also calculates the annual energy production. This calculation is performed for each potential site and populates spatially in GIS.

5 HYDROPOWER POTENTIAL ESTIMATE

The vast network of streams and rivers scattered across the accidental relief of Haiti’s mountains creates many sites where the implementation of hydropower facilities is feasible. However, these potential hydropower sites need to satisfy minimum selection criteria.

5.1 POTENTIAL SITES SPOTTING CRITERIA

For this study, a set of criteria was elaborated for the selection of a potential hydropower site. The criteria are as follow:

- The turbine house must be placed upstream of any existing permanent or semi-permanent diversion structure.
- The selected river needs to be perennial not seasonal. This is visually determined by comparing the historical aerial data from Google Earth which in many cases cover the rainy and the dry season.
- Locate the dam below or at the first upstream affluent, but not on the most upstream reach of a river where seasonal flow can occur.
- Minimum dam height is limited to 2 meters, while maximum dam height is limited to 55 meters.
- Location of a major dam and reservoir is excluded where a known fault line is present.
- Reservoir flood area shall not inundate cities.

5.2 SITE CLASSIFICATION

Many different classifications have been used to categorize hydroelectric projects. One common classification divided hydroelectric sites into three categories by head. These categories are:

- Low head for sites having a head ranging from 2 to 20 meters.
- Medium head for sites having a head ranging from 20 to 150 meters.
- High head for sites having a head greater than 150 meters.

In this study a different classification has been used. Potential sites have been classified by the amount of power that could be produced (size). The average yearly power is used in this classification. The different classifications are listed in table 5-1 along with the map icons used.

ICON	SITE CLASSIFICATION
	Pico (P < 50 KW)
	Micro (50 KW ≤ P < 100 KW)
	Mini (100 KW ≤ P < 500 KW)
	Small (500 KW ≤ P < 1,000 KW)
	Macro (1,000 KW ≤ P < 10,000 KW)
	Large (P > 10,000 KW)

Table 5-1 Average power output classification of hydropower plants

Besides the site classification based on the power output, a site identification scheme was created to locate a potential site geographically within Haiti’s administrative borders. There are ten administrative areas in Haiti known as “Departement”. Each “Departement” has been referred

by a two letters abbreviation. A site identification is the combination of a two letters abbreviation for Haiti, followed by a two letters abbreviation for the “Departement”, and finally the potential site number within the “Departement”. Table 5-2 illustrates the numbering scheme used in this study.

SITE IDENTIFICATION FORMAT	DEPARTEMENT ABBREVIATION	DEPARTEMENT
HTAR-01	AR	Artibonite
HTCT-01	CT	Centre
HTGA-01	GA	Grande-Anse
HTND-01	ND	Nord
HTNE-01	NE	Nord-Est
HTNO-01	NO	Nord-Ouest
HTNP-01	NP	Nippes
HTOT-01	OT	Ouest
HTSD-01	SD	Sud
HTSE-01	SE	Sud-Est

Table 5-2 Site identification numbering format

5.3 POTENTIAL SITES ESTIMATED CAPACITY

A total of 172 sites has been located, of which 7 are existing, 164 are new, and 1 site HTCT-03 “Dos Bocas” is redundant to site HTCT-04 “EDH GU-1”. The reason for this redundancy is that “Dos Bocas” straddles the Haitian-Dominican border and if constructed will prevent “EDH GU-1” to be implemented. All maps and exhibits list “Dos Bocas”, but its capacity is excluded in Haiti’s potential data. A summary of the potential sites estimated capacity is listed in table 5-3.

POTENTIAL	NUMBER OF SITES	MAXIMUM POWER (KW)	AVERAGE POWER (KW)	MINIMUM POWER (KW)	ANNUAL ENERGY (KWH)
Developed	7	53,491	38,861	20,645	340,419,354
Un-developed	164	233,554	156,665	69,860	1,372,430,279
Total	171	287,045	195,526	90,505	1,712,849,633

Table 5-3 General estimate of Haiti’s hydropower potential

Further information about this potential estimate can be accessed in Appendix D. In these maps all the sites are geographically located and numbered. Additional data about each site are also summarized in “General Summary Table” from this appendix. This table lists the general data for each site, the monthly potential power data, the yearly potential energy production data, and the site classification.

These sites are spatially distributed among the 10 “Departements” of the country and range in classification from Pico to Large as displayed in figure 19. The evaluated potential is theoretical and is conservative as a first estimate. An in depth engineering study of these sites is needed to further converge the estimate to a more accurate value. An overview of the distribution of these sites by “Departements” and size classification is summarized in table 5-4 below.

DEPARTEMENT	MAXIMUM POWER (KW)	ANNUAL ENERGY (KWH)	NUMBER OF SITES PER CLASSIFICATION					TOTAL	
			PICO	MICRO	MINI	SMALL	MACRO		LARGE
Artibonite	74,156	434,083,125	7	6	9	1	1	2	26
Centre	39,047	230,352,647	8	4	12	2	2	1	29
Grande-Anse	36,766	238,311,795	0	0	1	2	10	0	13
Nippes	6,434	48,696,507	0	3	0	0	2	0	5
Nord	3,197	17,896,633	1	1	5	1	0	0	8
Nord-Est	3,313	20,005,755	0	1	3	1	1	0	6
Nord-Ouest	5,062	26,944,476	8	3	2	0	1	0	14
Ouest	33,183	196,472,668	1	4	11	10	6	0	32
Sud	9,606	56,964,619	0	1	4	3	2	0	10
Sud-Est	22,790	102,702,054	2	2	10	4	3	0	21
TOTAL	233,554	1,372,430,279	27	25	57	24	28	3	164

Table 5-4 General theoretical hydroelectric potential of Haiti

From the 164 sites identified in the country, a total of 79 sites were selected as the most technically feasible as displayed in figure 30. The selection criteria excluded sites classified in the “Pico” category since this study could not in earnest locate all of them. There are far too numerous to be mapped out. The selection criterion is based on the ratio of the minimum power over the maximum power to be above 20 percent. Sites below this ratio will have to be optimized in order to meet this ratio. The optimization of sites was not attempted. An overview of the selected sites by “Departements” and size classification is summarized in table 5-5 below.

DEPARTEMENT	MAXIMUM POWER (KW)	ANNUAL ENERGY (KWH)	NUMBER OF SITES PER CLASSIFICATION					TOTAL	
			PICO	MICRO	MINI	SMALL	MACRO		LARGE
Artibonite	69,762	413,175,573	0	0	3	1	1	2	7
Centre	13,802	106,209,412	0	2	3	1	1	1	8
Grande-Anse	36,766	238,311,795	0	0	1	2	10	0	13
Nippes	6,313	48,179,478	0	2	0	0	2	0	4
Nord	2,324	13,400,811	0	1	5	0	0	0	6
Nord-Est	2,913	17,911,877	0	0	2	1	1	0	4
Nord-Ouest	1,041	5,336,364	0	2	2	0	0	0	4
Ouest	24,490	153,395,753	0	1	10	6	5	0	22
Sud	8,396	51,571,326	0	0	2	3	2	0	7
Sud-Est	3,240	18,981,452	0	0	2	1	1	0	4
TOTAL	169,047	1,066,473,841	0	8	30	15	23	3	79

Table 5-5 Selected feasible hydroelectric potential of Haiti

Figure 19 Spatial distribution of general hydroelectric sites of Haiti

Figure 20 Spatial distribution of general hydroelectric sites for Ouest Departement

Figure 21 Spatial distribution of general hydroelectric sites for Sud-Est Departement

Figure 22 Spatial distribution of general hydroelectric sites for Sud Departement

Figure 23 Spatial distribution of general hydroelectric sites for Grande Anse Departement

Figure 24 Spatial distribution of general hydroelectric sites for Nippes Departement

Figure 25 Spatial distribution of general hydroelectric sites for Artinonite Departement

Figure 26 Spatial distribution of general hydroelectric sites for Nord-Ouest Departement

Figure 27 Spatial distribution of general hydroelectric sites for Nord Departement

Figure 28 Spatial distribution of general hydroelectric sites for Nord-Est Departement

Figure 29 Spatial distribution of general hydroelectric sites for Centre Departement

Figure 30 Spatial distribution of selected hydroelectric sites of Haiti

Figure 31 Spatial distribution of selected hydroelectric sites for OUEST Department

Figure 32 Spatial distribution of selected hydroelectric sites for Sud-Est Departement

Figure 33 Spatial distribution of selected hydroelectric sites for Sud Departement

Figure 34 Spatial distribution of selected hydroelectric sites for Grande Anse Departement

Figure 35 Spatial distribution of selected hydroelectric sites for Nippes Departement

Figure 36 Spatial distribution of selected hydroelectric sites for Artibonite Departement

Figure 37 Spatial distribution of selected hydroelectric sites for Nord-Ouest Departement

Figure 38 Spatial distribution of selected hydroelectric sites for Nord Departement

Figure 39 Spatial distribution of selected hydroelectric sites for Nord-Est Departement

Figure 40 Spatial distribution of selected hydroelectric sites for Centre Departement

6 CONCLUSION

The main objective of this study was to provide a reliable and comprehensive estimate of the hydroelectric potential of Haiti. The GIS mapping approach that was implemented accomplished this objective. The GIS database that was created incorporated all the available data. The spatial data of the potential sites consolidates estimates from previous studies. A total of 164 sites totaling 233,554 KW has been identified. Amongst those, 79 potential sites totaling 169,047 KW have been selected as the most promising.

This study reveals that the hydrological data are very sparse. A water balance methodology has been applied and calibrated to estimate the river flows at sites of interest based on available data from gauging stations. There are still other potential sites that have not been recorded, but their capacity will not significantly change the estimate for the country.

This study demonstrates that the hydropower potential of Haiti is virtually untapped, and that many opportunities exist. The sites listed in both the general and the selected categories if developed will greatly improve the economic future of the country. The GIS database that was created could be used to further plan and prioritize the development of these sites.

The hydroelectric potential of Haiti consists of 164 sites ranging from 50 KW to over 10,000 KW for a cumulative total of 233,554 KW. From the spatially spotted sites, 79 were deemed to be the most feasible based solely on a 20% or above for the ratio of the minimum power over the maximum power. The cumulative capacity of these 79 sites is approximately 169,047 KW.

7 REFERENCES

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Appendix A

GIS Database References

[Haiti-Hydropower_Potential-Appendix-A.pdf](#)

Appendix B

Existing Climatology Data

[Haiti-Hydropower_Potential-Appendix-B.pdf](#)

Appendix C

Existing Selected River Gauging Stations Data

[Haiti-Hydropower_Potential-Appendix-C.pdf](#)

Appendix D

Hydroelectric Potential General Exhibits

[Haiti-Hydropower_Potential-Appendix-D.pdf](#)

Appendix E

Hydroelectric Potential Selected Sites Data Sheet

HAITI – GIS-based Hydropower Potential Mapping Atlas

[Haiti-Hydropower Potential-Appendix-E - 1.pdf](#)

[Haiti-Hydropower Potential-Appendix-E - 2.pdf](#)

[Haiti-Hydropower Potential-Appendix-E - 3.pdf](#)

[Haiti-Hydropower Potential-Appendix-E - 4.pdf](#)

[Haiti-Hydropower Potential-Appendix-E - 5.pdf](#)

Appendix F

Presentation

[Haiti-Hydropower_Potential-Appendix-F.pdf](#)